

D3.5: 1st Design Guidelines for Open Sensor fabrication

WP3 – Collective sensing models and tools

D3.5: 1st Design Guidelines for Open Sensor fabrication

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1 Executive summary

The current report is the first version of the design guidelines for the hackAIR open sensor fabrication that describes the implementation details of three open hardware solutions along with an initial version of user guidelines for the construction of each one. The aforementioned solutions will be used as the open hardware devices for data acquisition in the hackAIR project. There will be an update on this report on June 2017 which will include evaluation results from newly introduced PM sensors (i.e. Plantower PMS5003, iNovafitness SD011), as these two sensors became commercially available in Europe after the completion of our performance tests.

The proposed hardware solutions are the following:

- An Arduino based air quality monitoring node
- A Programmable System-on-Chip (PSoC) based air quality monitoring node (BLEAir)
- A Commercial of the Shelf (COTS) air quality monitoring node.

2 Design methodology-Sensors and processing node fundamentals

2.1 Introduction

The following table summarises the basic specifications of the adopted solutions regarding the Arduino node and the PSoC node implementations.

Table 1: Main characteristics of Arduino based and BLEAir nodes

	Arduino based node	BLEAir node
<i>Processing Device</i>	Arduino	PSoC/PRoC BLE
<i>Main Purpose</i>	Home Monitoring (indoor or outdoor)	Beacon measuring Node
<i>Approximate Cost(€)</i>	Arduino (25) + sensor(43) + power bank/wall mount (7) + WiFi/Ethernet (10/15)	PSoC/PRoC BLE module(10/20) + laser sensor(43) + power bank (7)
<i>Market availability</i>	Widely available in electronic components stores and European DIY distributors (Farnell, Digikey, DfRobot, Mouser, CoolComponents, EBVElectronik, etc.)	
<i>Power Supply</i>	Wall mount PSU	Wall mount USB
<i>Battery Requirements</i>	5V Power Bank (min 2600mAh)	5V Power Bank (min 2600mAh)
<i>Minimum Battery Operation</i>	20 hours	2 days
<i>Connectivity</i>	Wireless and Ethernet network	Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE)
<i>Connectivity to Mobile</i>	During system initialization and configuration	YES
<i>Method for Data transmission</i>	Through WiFi	BLE beacon to smartphone and then any type of internet connection
<i>WiFi Availability</i>	YES	NO
<i>Setup Procedure</i>	Through Arduino IDE + WiFi	Low cost programmer (5-10€) + free

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		software + hackAIR firmwares for uploading
<i>User Programming</i>	hackAIR library + Arduino IDE	Not required (but available if user wants to modify initial firmware code)
<i>Geolocation</i>	Yes using user's profile geolocation details (or from optional GPS shield)	Yes (From mobile)
<i>Assembly</i>	Guidelines using COTS	Guidelines using modules
<i>Other Characteristics</i>	Big Arduino community	More focused to specific users and up to date gadget users
		Low Power Consumption
	Other (lower cost) sensors available but with poorer accuracy	
	Better for ordinary people	Better for experimenters
	Can be used as school project	Can be used as maker/hacker project
	Ability to use power banks for extended operation time	

The design requirements for the Arduino based node as well as BLEAir nodes are presented in detail in the current document. The detailed design and implementation of the COTS will be presented in the deliverable that will be submitted on June 2017. Apart from the different approaches that are implemented for each type of node, there are some features which are common to both devices regarding sensor interfaces. Thus, a short presentation of the selected sensors and their requirements is also included in this document.

Arduino and BLEAir implementations are presented in Figures 1 and 2 and, finally, instructions in the form of implementation guidelines are introduced. Regarding the design of COTS air quality estimation system, its aim is to use non-electronics materials that may be found in hardware stores so that users build a system that is able to depict the dust concentration using paper and/or fibrous filters. Using a smartphone's camera, a photo of the filter is taken and uploaded to the hackAIR platform in order to be analyzed by means of image processing algorithms.

Figure 1: Assembled Arduino node

Figure 2. Assembled BLEAir node

2.2 Low cost PM sensors

The Arduino based node as well as the BLEAir node share some common features along with many differences as presented in Table 1. Except from the common type of power supply unit that they are able to use (battery or power bank), their major common feature is the type of sensors that they will use to obtain PM measurements and transmit them to the hackAIR platform. The output of each of the proposed sensor (after the necessary conversions) is processed by the corresponding Micro Controller Unit (MCU) preparing the data that will be transmitted either wirelessly (by means of WiFi or Bluetooth protocols) or using Ethernet.

The sensors included in Table 2 are the potential sensing devices that will be used for PM sensing in the hackAIR open hardware design. A crucial requirement for the selection of a PM sensor is its low cost along with the high accuracy and repeatability specifications.

All the sensors are based on the same measurement principle, which is known as *optical scattering*: the airborne particles flowing across a light beam scatter the incident light; the scattered light reaches an optical detector which generates a signal proportional to the received light intensity. Since each sensor implements the measurement principle in a different way according to its manufacturing process, it was decided to evaluate their performance in order to select the most appropriate to meet the goal of this project, which is to design an adaptive open low cost hardware to estimate particulate pollution. This will be achieved through calibration and evaluation to classify the sensors according to their performance. Results regarding the performance of sensors with id 1 to 6 are presented in this deliverable. Performance results for sensors with id 7 and 8 will be reported in the update of this report (June 2017) since these two sensors became commercially available in Europe after the completion of performance tests of sensors 1 to 6.

Table 2: Main technical characteristic of selected sensors

id	SENSOR TYPE	Light beam	Signal Output	Output signal form	Forced Air flow	Result (Particles)	Sensing range	PRICE* (euro)
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							($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	
1	sharp GP2Y1010AU0F	LED	Analog	Voltage	No	Total number	0-600	12
2	sharp DN7C3CA006	LED	Analog	Voltage	Yes (by fan)	Total number	0-500	20
3	amphenol SM-PWM-01	LED	Digital	Pulses (PWM)	No	Big ($>PM_{2.5}$) and small ($<PM_{2.5}$)	4-340***	18
4	sharp GP2Y1023AU0F	LED	Digital	Pulses (PWM)	Yes (heating resistor)	Total number	0-300	15
5	Shinyei PPD42NS	LED	Digital	Pulses (PWM)	No	Big ($>PM_{2.5}$) and small ($<PM_{1.0}$)	1-500**	18
6	DFRobot SEN0117	Laser	Digital	Serial output	Yes (by fan)	$PM_{1.0}$, $PM_{2.5}$, PM_{10} individual values in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	0-500	45
7	Plantower PMS5003	Laser	Digital	Serial output	Yes (by fan)	$PM_{1.0}$, $PM_{2.5}$, PM_{10} individual values in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	0-500	28
8	iNovaFit SDS011	Laser	Digital	Serial output	Yes (by fan)	$PM_{2.5}$, PM_{10} individual values in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	0-999	36

*prices derived at 1/5/2016 from at least one international distributor

** Converted values from [1] since Shinyei PPD42NS output results in particles/283ml-0.01cf.

*** Converted values using [2]

As presented earlier, there are three communication protocols to attach the sensors to the Arduino and the BLEAir processing devices. These types of data interface are:

- Analog reading (range 0.5-3.6V max)
- Digital (pulse width reading)
- Serial by means of Universal Asynchronous Receiver/Transmitter (UART)

The proposed implementations for each device fulfill all the above interface requirements. In addition, since a) to c) requirements are the industry standards they will be included in any forthcoming PM sensors [3], [4]. Under this approach all the proposed implementations presented below are capable to support various PM sensors providing in this way guaranteed sustainability to the hackAIR project since the nodes are designed in a way that will also allow the use of other $PM_{2.5}/PM_{10}$ sensors than the ones tested now (in case these sensors are compatible with data interfaces as presented above).

2.3 Sensor evaluation

A preliminary comparison between the sensors presented in Table 2 and an Air Quality Monitor (AQM) system (Dylos DC1100 Pro) was performed. This AQM system was selected since it is the only commercial low-cost (under \$400) instrument which results are closer to those of reference PM monitors (MetOne Beta Attenuation Monitor which costs \$15000) [5] [6]. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the performance of each selected sensor and to propose (in hierarchical order) the most appropriate ones according to the requirements presented in Section 2.1.

The first step to the current study is to convert the output values from each examined sensor (as well as from the commercial AQM) to the $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ scale. As presented in Table 2, each sensor provides raw output values which must be converted to the $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ scale (except from the SEN0117 which provides its output directly to $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for $PM_{1.0}$, $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10}). Each sensor needs a different conversion formula and for this reason we adopted the recommendations for manufacturers' datasheets or reference studies for each tested sensor (GP2Y1010AU0F [7], DN7C3CA006 [8], SM-PWM-01 [9], GP2Y1023AU0F [10], PPD42NS [11], DYLOS DC1100 pro [2])

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All sensors (along with AQM) were installed in a fixed base and the data were acquired by an Arduino Mega. Measurements took place in short and long-term cycles of measurements. All the examined sensors acquired data at a high sampling rate (typically 20 per minute). An averaging was performed and the resulting value represents the 0.5 minute average for short term measurements and 1 hour average for long term measurements. During the short term measurements (for 1 hour period) the sensors were installed indoors where a forced sudden air flow (by means of a high speed fan) was produced in order to spread room dust in the air. In Figure 3 the results from 1hr data acquisition (regarding PM_{2.5}) are presented. Figure 4 presents the corresponding results for PM₁₀ detected particles. Long term measurement took place outdoors for 200 hours. Results are presented in Figure 5 for PM_{2.5} and in Figure 6 for PM₁₀.

According to the preliminary results, the examined sensors fall into two categories: (i) Acceptable with good correlation (SEN0117 and PPD42NS) and (ii) under consideration with low-intermediate correlation (GP2Y1010AU0F, DN7C3CA006, SM-PWM-01 and GP2Y1023AU0F). For this reason we propose the replacement of the SM-PWM-01 and GP2Y1023AU0F sensors by newer, low cost laser sensors such as Plantower PMS5003 [12] and iNovafitness SD011 [13].

Figure 3. PM_{2.5} hourly data for examined sensors and reference instrument (DC1100pro)

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Figure 4. PM10 hourly data for examined sensors and reference instrument (DC1100pro)

Figure 5. PM2.5 hourly averaged data for examined sensors and reference instrument (DC1100pro)

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Figure 6. PM10 hourly averaged data for examined sensors and reference instrument (DC1100pro)

2.4 BLEAir design methodology

The purpose of the BLEAir node is to implement a PM measuring device in the form of a Bluetooth beacon. A beacon is a proximal wireless notification service which is based on the concept of broadcasting small pieces of information¹. Beacon transmitters broadcast small data packets to any Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) capable device without the need of authenticated bonding. The BLEAir node will acquire data values from attached sensors and it will transmit (through Bluetooth) to a nearby smartphone the value of PM particles in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. A corresponding application in the smartphone will receive the PM data, it will geo-tag them and finally, it will push them to the hackAIR server. Each PSoC module has a unique address (silicon coded) that will be used for authentication purposes.

A BLE device can operate in four different device roles. Depending on the role, the devices behave differently:

- A *Peripheral* device is an advertiser that is connectable and can operate as a slave in a connection (e.g. heart rate sensor).
- A *Central* device scans for advertisers and can initiate connections. It operates as a master in one or more connections (e.g. Smartphones and computers).
- A *Broadcaster* is a non-connectable advertiser (e.g. a temperature sensor that broadcasts the current temperature).
- An *Observer* scans for advertisements, but cannot initiate connections (e.g. a remote LCD that receives the temperature data and presents them).

Roles a) and b) are connection-based while roles c) and d) are used for one-directional communication. The most appropriate device roles for beacon applications (and for hackAIR also) are the Peripheral and the Broadcaster. Both of them send the same type of advertisements with the exception of one specific flag that indicates whether it is connectable or non-connectable [14]. The role of the BLEAir node that will be selected for the purposes of hackAIR is the non-connectable beacon in broadcasting mode. Under this approach, the BLEAir node will only transmit information that is acquired by attached sensors. As the non-connectable broadcasting does not activate any receiving capabilities, it achieves the lowest possible power consumption by simply waking up, transmitting data and going back to sleep.

¹<http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7312045?reload=true&arnumber=7312045>

<http://www.gsma.com/digitalcommerce/wp-content/uploads/2013/10/A-guide-to-BLE-beacons-FINAL-18-Sept-14.pdf>

http://www.cisco.com/c/dam/en/us/solutions/collateral/enterprise-networks/connected-mobile-experiences/ibeacon_faq.pdf

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The core of the BLEAir system is the PSoC 4 (Programmable System On Chip) BLE from Cypress Inc (www.cypress.com). Cypress's PSoC 4 BLE (5) integrates a low power 32bit ARM Cortex-M0 processor with a Bluetooth Low Energy Transceiver and various analog and digital programmable peripherals for mixed signal design on a single chip solution for the Internet of Things. The device architecture provides a flexible internal configuration for each subsystem by allowing the user to internally route digital and analog signals.

Figure 7: Architecture overview of PSoC 4 BLE (photo from cypress.com)

The PSoC includes multiple analog peripherals like Analog to Digital Converter (ADC), operational amplifiers, multiple current DACs, analog comparators and Cypress's CapSense technology. It also includes digital peripherals such as timers, pulse width modulators, glitch filters, serial communication blocks (SCB) and finally several Universal Digital Blocks (UDB) which consist of a PLD (Programmable Logic Device) and a Datapath (Arithmetic Logic Unit (ALU) and registers).

PSoC 4 BLE provides a cost-effective and small footprint alternative to the combination of an MCU and a BLE radio. The programmable analog and digital subsystems allow flexibility and dynamic fine-tuning of the design using PSoC Creator, the schematic-based design tool for developing PSoC 4 BLE applications. To develop a BLE application, users do not need technical knowledge of the BLE complex protocol stack. The Cypress company provides a free easy-to-configure graphical user interface (GUI) based on the BLE Component in PSoC Creator that simplifies the implementation procedure. We can configure the BLE Component in minutes using a GUI, enabling users to jump-start their BLE design. The PSoC 4 BLE offers a current consumption of 150 nA while retaining the SRAM contents, programmable logic, and the ability to wake up from an interrupt. It consumes 1.3 μ A in Deep-Sleep mode while maintaining an active BLE link. A combination of these low-power modes provides a best-in-class system power consumption for battery-operated BLE designs.

2.5 Arduino node design methodology

The Arduino node will be built around an Arduino/Genuino UNO [15] electronics prototyping and development system. The Arduino node targets users with little experience in electronics. Avoiding the enumeration of the benefits from the Arduino selection (since its popularity allows relevant sources and articles to be widely available) the current section focuses on the design methodology only. The initial requirements for the sensors presented in Table 2 can be fulfilled by Arduino UNO since it can provide Analog reading (0-5V), more than one PWM counter, as well as direct serial connection through its UART (hardware from pins 0,1 or software serial from other digital input pins). Data will be transmitted using Ethernet or WiFi protocol (using the corresponding shield). Authentication will be provided in the form of a token for each Arduino board.

2.6 COTS design methodology

The COTS air quality estimation system is based on the following technique. The measurement methodology is based on pumping air from the free environment and guiding it through a filter. The size and the quantity of the particles that are deposited on the filter can provide information regarding the air quality in terms of PM pollution. The main information is extracted from the filter. It is expected that Computer vision algorithms that will be developed by the hackAIR partners (until June 2017) will provide highly accurate results in order to pick information for the quality of the air in the free environment. Pictures of the filters will be provided from the users who participate in the project. No time limit on the measurement time is enforced.

After removing the filter from the air pump the user must take a high-resolution photo, using a fixed focus magnifying lens (clip lens hereafter) widely available at a cost well below 10€. Figure 8 shows such a configuration where the user is able to attach the lens in front of their smartphone's camera. The captured photo will be automatically processed inside hackAIR's app and uploaded to the hackAIR servers. The goal is to estimate a level of PM air pollution from the optical estimated concentration of particles in the filter.

Figure 8: A clip lens attached in front of smartphone's camera

3 Development tools

3.1 BLEAir development tools

The PSoC BLE module can be programmed using the Cypress' PSoC Creator software [16], a state of the art Integrated Development Environment (IDE) that provides the necessary tools for hardware and software editing, thus enabling the user to design mixed signal applications with BLE connectivity. Its schematic capture allows fast graphical configuration and internal connection of peripherals and also allows a hierarchical design by creating custom schematic components. After building the applications the IDE automatically generates the necessary libraries to fully control the components with simple C functions (e.g. MyPeripheral_Start). The PSoC creator also includes a large number of well documented predesigned components for multiple functions.

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- ① 100+ pre-verified, production- ready Components
- ② Drag and drop Components onto a schematic design
- ③ Easily set-up and configure Components
- ④ Develop, Build and Debug your project

Figure 9. PSoC programming sequence using PSoC Creator

The PSoC Components are analog and digital “virtual chips,” represented by an icon that users can drag-and-drop into a design and configure to suit a broad array of application requirements (Figure 9). Each component in the rich mixed-signal Cypress Component Catalog is configured with a Component Customizer and includes a full set of dynamically generated API libraries. Once the PSoC system has been configured, firmware can be written, compiled, and debugged within PSoC Creator or exported to top 3rd party IDEs from IAR, Keil, and Eclipse.

An alternative solution for the users that only want to “burn” a precompiled firmware to a PSoC is the use of PSoC programmer software. Under this approach, the user has to complete only two actions after opening the software: a) reading a .hex file b) pressing the “Program” button as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. PSoC programmer sequence of actions for “burning” firmware to a PSoC: reading (red arrow) – programming PSoC (green arrow)

To program a PSoC 4 BLE device with applications designed in PSoC Creator or using the PSoC programmer software the user can simply select the target hardware using the device selector, connecting the device to a MiniProg3 USB programmer (Figure 11) and start the programming or debugging process. Alternative solutions to the MiniProg3 programmer are the low cost KitProg programmer that comes as a detachable part in Cypress’s PSoC 5LP Prototyping Kit (Figure 12) and the CY8CKIT-042-BLE, which is a development board in the Arduino style board (Figure 13). The difference is that MiniProg3 provides programming and debugging capabilities and costs 89\$ while KitProg is only a programmer but costs 10\$. The CY8CKIT-042-BLE is a programmer and development kit and includes two BLE modules with total cost of 49\$. All the above three devices can be used for all hackAIR BLE designs and programming operations and the user need to buy only one of those in the first time.

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Design Filter on Device	Architecture	Max Frequency (MHz)	Flash (KB)	SRAM (KB)	Package	IOB	ADC	Bit DAC	Dcmp	Comparator	DPB	Analog [SCCT] Blocks	Timer/Counter/PWM
CY8C3866AA-038	PSoC 3 (8051)	67	64	8	100-TQFP	24	1x 20-bit Delta Sigma	4	4	4	1	4	
CY8C3866AA-039	PSoC 3 (8051)	67	64	8	100-TQFP	24	1x 20-bit Delta Sigma	4	4	4	1	4	
CY8C3866AA-040	PSoC 3 (8051)	67	64	8	100-TQFP	24	1x 20-bit Delta Sigma	4	4	4	1	4	
CY8C3866AA-055	PSoC 3 (8051)	67	64	8	100-TQFP	24	1x 20-bit Delta Sigma	4	4	4	1	4	
CY8C3866AA-035	PSoC 3 (8051)	67	64	8	100-TQFP	24	1x 20-bit Delta Sigma	4	4	4	1	4	
CY8C3866AA-039	PSoC 3 (8051)	67	64	8	100-TQFP	24	1x 20-bit Delta Sigma	4	4	4	1	4	
CY8C3866AA-040	PSoC 3 (8051)	67	64	8	100-TQFP	24	1x 20-bit Delta Sigma	4	4	4	1	4	
CY8C3866AA-206	PSoC 3 (8051)	67	64	8	100-TQFP	20	1x 20-bit Delta Sigma	2	2	2	1	-	
CY8C3866AA-208	PSoC 3 (8051)	67	64	8	100-TQFP	24	1x 20-bit Delta Sigma	2	2	2	1	2	
CY8C3866FN-210	PSoC 3 (8051)	67	64	8	72-WLCSP	24	1x 20-bit Delta Sigma	4	4	4	1	4	
CY8C3866LT-030	PSoC 3 (8051)	67	64	8	68-QFN	24	1x 20-bit Delta Sigma	4	4	4	1	4	
CY8C3866LT-067	PSoC 3 (8051)	67	64	8	48-QFN	24	1x 20-bit Delta Sigma	4	2	4	1	4	
CY8C3866LT-068	PSoC 3 (8051)	67	64	8	48-QFN	24	1x 20-bit Delta Sigma	4	2	4	1	4	

Figure 11. Programming PSoC using MiniProg3 USB programmer

Figure 12. KitProg detachable programmer

Figure 13. CY8CKIT-042-BLE development kit

3.2 Arduino node development tools

The necessary development tools for the Arduino node are an Arduino/Genuino UNO board and the Arduino IDE (ver. 1.6 and above). The use of Arduino IDE is widely spread so users who are not familiar with it can find many quick-start guides. It is beyond the scope of this report to provide a tutorial for the use of Arduino IDE.

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Before IDE's first run, the hackAIR library should be installed. The user downloads the latest version from hackAIR's website and decompresses it inside "Arduino\libraries" subfolder. The user can verify the existence of the library by exploring the "libraries" menu item.

For the Ethernet connection, an Ethernet shield with WIZ5xxx chip can be used. For the WiFi connection, a custom shield based on ESP8266 WiFi module is proposed below. A smartphone with a proposed WiFi manager app is desirable (but not necessary) in case the user wants to transfer the Arduino node between different WiFi networks (thus having different SSID/keys combinations).

3.3 COTS development tools

The necessary development tool for the COTS is a device that absorbs air from the environment (for example: an air pump) and a filter (for example: surgical mask or coffee filter), through which the air will be forced. Users should be careful to close tightly the inflation part of the air pump with the filter so that no air can travel through the system. This can be done using rubber bands, a pair of magnets or a commercial tape. While taking a photo a clip lens is proposed to be used to picture the particles of the filter with enough light (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Air Pump with the filter attached

4 Design guidelines - hackAIR nodes

4.1 BLEAir node design guidelines

The design requirements for the BLEAir node fall into three main categories:

- I. Sensor Interfacing
- II. Power supply
- III. Bluetooth transmission

The first requirement can be easily satisfied since the PSoC architecture provides all the necessary components to complete the whole sequence of interfacing. More specifically, for interfacing with analogue sensors a 12bit SAR ADC was selected. The top-design level of BLEAir for analogue sensors is presented in Figure 15. Regarding power supply, PSoC 4 BLE can operate in a wide range of voltages; from 1.9V to 5.5V. Thus, by using 5V from a USB port (by means of a portable power bank) the onboard regulators of PSoC module can manage all the power requirements (including the sensor's fan which requires 5V). Finally, the Bluetooth transmission can be easily fulfilled since the BLE subsystem is embedded within the PSoC 4 BLE module.

Figure 15. Top-level design for BLEAir node using analogue output sensors

For the remaining two categories of sensors (PWM and Serial output) the top-level designs are presented below. For PWM sensors, there are two designs: one for GP2Y1023AU0F (which uses a single pulse LED mode) and is presented in Figure 16 and one for SW-PWM-01 sensor (which uses a dual pulse LED mode) and is presented in Figure 17. The difference between them is the number of required counters.

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Figure 16. Top-level design for BLEAir node using GP2Y1023AU0F sensor

Figure 17. Top-level design for BLEAir node using SM-PWM-01C sensor

Finally, for the serial output sensor, a corresponding UART is the only subsystem that should be altered in relation with previous designs and is presented in Figure 18.

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Figure 18. Top-level design for BLEAir node using SEN0177 serial output sensor

The BLE data packet will follow the individual characteristics of each sensor and its design's uniqueness. The proposed format for the BLE data packets is shown in Figure 19.

BLE Advertisement Packets

Figure 19. BLEAir node data packets for corresponding sensors

Where:

- Flags & Name contains manufacturer id, unique address and user specific data
- Sensor type is a number that corresponds as id to each sensor
- Custom user data reserved for future use (i.e. for battery level)
- Total particles, Big particles, Small particles, PM1, PM2.5 and PM10 are the corresponding values from each sensor in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

4.2 Arduino node design guidelines

The requirements (I and II) described in Chapter 4.1 can be easily fulfilled by the Arduino node. Power supply for the attached sensors can be provided by 5V pin since the heaviest power consuming sensor requires up to 160mA (less than the theoretical amount of 460mA through a 500mA USB port power supply). Analogue readings will be possible using pins A0 to A5 while PWM reading as well as serial reading is possible using digital input pins. Users should only plug each sensor's cable to the corresponding input (according to the instructions provided in Chapter 7) and program the Arduino using a simple sketch (which will be described in Chapter 6).

The core of the system is the hackAIR library. The Arduino hackAIR library is a collection of utilities and functions that help the user in using a variety of air quality sensors with the Arduino platform. The library includes all the necessary calibration information and transfer functions for the supported sensors so that the user can quickly and easily take readings without having to spend time learning how each sensor works while it allows advanced users to fine tune their sensor setup. Lastly, the library contains an abstraction layer for creating and sending network requests through Ethernet or WiFi so that data can be submitted to the hackAIR platform.

Data transmission to the hackAIR server will be performed by means of Ethernet or WiFi connection. The Ethernet option requires an Ethernet shield with WIZ5xxx chip while for the WiFi connection a prototype board (hackAIR WiFi shield) was designed and developed using ESP8266 module along with required components. The hackAIR WiFi shield can act as a complete solution because, apart from the WiFi circuitry, it embeds all the external components required by the sensors (including the screw terminal and pin connectors). The schematic capture of the proposed shield is presented in Fig.20 while a prototype of the shield is presented in Fig.21

Figure 20. Schematic capture of the proposed hackAIR WiFi shield

Figure 21. Prototype of the hackAIR WiFi shield

A problem that some users may face is the change of WiFi network credentials. Since the SSID and the key are passed to Arduino inside the sketch they remain unchanged until next programming sequence. This is not practical if the user wants to use another network. For this reason, an additional library will be used (hackAIR-wifi.h) to enable the user to select which WiFi network will be used before initialization of connections. The actions that the users will follow are:

- when the WiFi shield powers up, the node enters Station mode and tries to connect to a previously saved Access Point
- if this is unsuccessful (or no previous network is saved) the node moves the ESP into Access Point mode and spins up a DNS and WebServer (default ip 192.168.4.1)
- by means of any WiFi enabled device with a browser (computer, phone, tablet) connect to the newly created Access Point.
- because of the Captive Portal and the DNS server user will get a 'Join to network' type of popup
- User selects one of the access points scanned, enters password, clicks save
- Arduino reboots and connects to internet using the selected WiFi network

A graphical representation of the above is presented in Figure 22.

The first time power is applied to a freshly programmed Arduino node the ESP WiFi module will start in AP (Access Point) mode. By connecting to this access point the user can select which AP should be used by the node for transmitting data to the hackAIR servers. After a suitable access point is selected and tested, the node will reboot, this time into Station Mode, and connect to the selected AP for internet connectivity.

Figure 22 presents the setup process step-by-step. The selected network can be reset by reprogramming the device. Due to the open source nature of the firmware, the maker community is able to make changes to this setup process as required, for example, using a physical button press to reset the network selection.

Figure 22. Use of smartphone to provide network's credentials to hackAIR's WiFi shield

4.3 COTS design guidelines

No interference from the users on the filter is allowed. The users should not touch the surface of the filter in order to avoid polluting the filter. A white filter is proposed to be used so that the identification of particles is easier. It is necessary to mention that the users should avoid measuring indoors or near highly polluted spots since this will lead to inaccurate PM concentration estimation (e.g. placing the filter at the exhaust of a car or next to a fire place chimney since the results will not be representative of the wider area of measurements). The filter must have a circle shape with dimensions larger than a 2 euro coin (see Figure 23). The distance from the smartphone and the filter when taking a photo depends on the camera.

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Figure 23. Preparation and size of the Filter

The acquired image will be further processed so that the system estimates the number of particles and thus their concentration since the dimensions of the filter paper as well as the distance from the lens to the paper is fixed which will be ensured considering that the users will select the proposed equipment (lens type and filter type). A typical acquired image is shown in Figure 24 while the thresholding result is shown in Figure 25. Using a cell detection algorithm, the system is able to count and classify the black dots in Figure 24 and thus (assuming that all black dots are particles) estimate the concentration.

Figure 24. Captured image of filter from smartphone's camera with cliplen

Figure 25. Part of image in Figure 23 after thresholding

5 Equipment list and technical specifications

5.1 BLEAir equipment

- Air Quality Beacon Printed Circuit Board (PCB)
 - Analog sensors PCB (use with DN7C3CA006, GP2Y1010AU0F, GP2Y1023AU0F, SM-PWM-01C and PPD42NS) as shown in Figure 26a
 - Serial Sensor PCB (use with SEN0177) as shown in Figure 26b.
- Dual male 1.2mm headers
- Male 1.2mm header (optional)
- 1x 150Ω Resistor
- 1x 220μF/16V electrolytic capacitor
- Dust density sensor (any sensor mentioned above)
- Sensor connector (provided by sensor vendor)
- USB type-b female with shield (through hole connector)
- PSoC 4 BLE Module (CY8CKIT-142) or compatible
- MiniProg3 programmer and debugger or KitProg (included in CY8CKIT-059)
- Soldering iron & solder

Figure 26. PCBs for analog/digital sensors (a) and for serial sensor (b) for use with BLEAir node

5.2 Arduino node equipment

- hackAIR WiFi shield PCB (Figure 27)
- PCB screw terminals
- Male 1.2mm header
- Arduino stackable header pins (set)

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- 1x 150Ω Resistor
- 1x 220μF/16V electrolytic capacitor
- 2x 10nF capacitor
- 2x 10μF/16V electrolytic capacitor
- 2x 100nF capacitor
- LD1117S33CTR regulator
- SN74LVC245A shifter
- ESP8266-01 module
- Dust density sensor (any sensor mentioned above)
- Sensor connector (provided by sensor vendor)
- Arduino/Genuino UNO or any compatible technology
- Soldering iron & solder

Figure 27. PCB for hackAIR WiFi shield

5.3 COTS equipment

- Air inflation system (e.g. air pump)
 - Filter (Surgical mask, coffee filter)
 - Something to hold the filter (rubber band, magnet, commercial tape)
- Smartphone
 - Fixed focus 6x macro cellphone lens (e.g. Lieqi-006 [17])

6 Software

6.1 BLEAir software

The software for BLEAir node comes in two forms:

- Ready made project files for using with PSoC creator
- Precompiled .hex files for using with PSoC programmer

Ready-made project files are complete packages including all the elements (main routines, libraries and support files) needed by users that will use the PSoC Creator software. This approach ensures that the PSoC solution, it is fully customizable and provides the ultimate configuration solution but it is suggested for more experienced users. In the initial stage the users can tweak the readymade source files for each type of sensor as presented below (comments are in green).

6.1.1 MAIN.C routine for analogue sensors

```

/* =====
 * Air Quality Beacon, part of the hackAIR project.
 * Freely available under CC BY 4.0
 *
 *
 * Author: George Doxastakis gdoxastakis.ee@gmail.com
 * Technology Transfer & Smart Solutions
 * TEI of Athens
 * http://research.ee.teiath.gr/ttss/
 *
 * http://www.hackAIR.eu/
 */
#include <project.h>

/* Function prototypes */
void StackEventHandler(uint32 event, void* eventParam);
int16 readParticles();
uint8 getQualityIndex(uint16 totalConcentration);

/* ADV payload dta structure */
extern CYBLE_GAPP_DISC_MODE_INFO_T cyBle_discoveryModeInfo;
#define advPayload (cyBle_discoveryModeInfo.advData->advData)

int main()
{
    CyGlobalIntEnable; /* Enable global interrupts. */

    /* Start CYBLE component and register the generic event handler */
    CyBle_Start(StackEventHandler);

    ADC_Start();
    ADC_StartConvert();
    for(;;)
    {
        int16 val=readParticles(); //Perform sensor measurement

        /* Dynamic payload will be continuously updated */
        advPayload[19] = 0x02; //Sensor ID: 0x02 for DN7C3CA006 or 0x03 for
GP2Y1010AU0F
        advPayload[23] = val>>8; //High byte of sensor measurement
        advPayload[24] = val&0xFF; //Low byte of sensor measurement
        CyBle_GapUpdateAdvData(cyBle_discoveryModeInfo.advData,
cyBle_discoveryModeInfo.scanRspData); //Update Advertisement Packet

```

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```
CyBle_ProcessEvents();

CyDelay(500); //Measurement delay
}
}

void StackEventHandler(uint32 event, void *eventParam)
{
    switch(event)
    {
        case CYBLE_EVT_STACK_ON:
            /* BLE stack is on. Start BLE advertisement */
            CyBle_GappStartAdvertisement(CYBLE_ADVERTISING_FAST);
            break;

        default:
            break;
    }
}

/*****
* NAME :          int16 readParticles()
*
* DESCRIPTION :   Read sensor measurement
* OUTPUTS :
*               int16 Dust concentration in ug/m^3
*/
int16 readParticles(){
    int i;
    int sum=0;

    for(i=0;i<10;i++){ // Average of 10 measurements
        Sensor_Power_Write(0); // Turn LED on
        CyDelayUs(280); // Specified delay
        sum+=ADC_CountsTo_mVolts(0, ADC_GetResult16(0)); // Get output voltage
        CyDelayUs(40); // Specified delay
        Sensor_Power_Write(1); // Turn LED off
        CyDelay(10); // Cycle delay
    }
    sum/=10; // Get average

    uint16 senDat=(int16)(1000.0f*((0.172f * (sum/1000.0f)) - 0.0999f)); // Sensor
transfer function

    return senDat;
}

/* [] END OF FILE */
```

6.1.2 MAIN.C routine for PWM (two pulse LED) sensors

```
/* =====
* Air Quality Beacon, part of the hackAIR project.
* Freely available under CC BY 4.0
*
*
* Author: George Doxastakis gdoxastakis.ee@gmail.com
* Technology Transfer & Smart Solutions
* TEI of Athens
* http://research.ee.teiath.gr/ttss/
```


D3.5: 1st Design Guidelines for Open Sensor fabrication

```
*
* http://www.hackAIR.eu/
*/
#include <project.h>

/* Function prototypes */
void StackEventHandler(uint32 event, void* eventParam);
char* readParticles();

/* ADV payload dta structure */
extern CYBLE_GAPP_DISC_MODE_INFO_T cyBle_discoveryModeInfo;
#define advPayload (cyBle_discoveryModeInfo.advData->advData)

int main()
{
    CyGlobalIntEnable; /* Enable global interrupts. */

    /* Start CYBLE component and register the generic event handler */
    CyBle_Start(StackEventHandler);

    Timer_Large_Start();
    Timer_Small_Start();
    for(;;)
    {
        char *val=readParticles(); //Perform sensor measurement

        /* Dynamic payload will be continuously updated */
        advPayload[19] = 0x05; //Sensor ID: 0x05 for SM-PWM-01C or 0x06 for PPD42N
        advPayload[23] = val[0]; //High byte of large particle value
        advPayload[24] = val[1]; //Low byte of large particle value
        advPayload[25] = val[2]; //High byte of small particle value
        advPayload[26] = val[3]; //Low byte of small particle value
        CyBle_GapUpdateAdvData(cyBle_discoveryModeInfo.advData,
        cyBle_discoveryModeInfo.scanRspData); //Update Advertisement Packet

        CyBle_ProcessEvents();

        CyDelay(500); //Measurement delay
    }
}

void StackEventHandler(uint32 event, void *eventParam)
{
    switch(event)
    {
        case CYBLE_EVT_STACK_ON:
            /* BLE stack is on. Start BLE advertisement */
            CyBle_GappStartAdvertisement(CYBLE_ADVERTISING_FAST);
            break;

        default:
            break;
    }
}

/*****
* NAME :          char* readParticles()
*
* DESCRIPTION :   Read sensor measurement
* OUTPUTS :
*               char* Large Particles (2 bytes) and Small Particles (2 bytes)
*****/
```


D3.5: 1st Design Guidelines for Open Sensor fabrication

```
*/
char* readParticles(){
    int i;
    int sum=0;
    static char dat[4];
    for(i=0;i<10;i++){ // Average of 10 measurements
        while(!PWM_Large_Read()); // Wait for previous pulse
        while(PWM_Large_Read()); // Wait for falling edge
        while(!PWM_Large_Read()); // Wait for rising edge
        CyDelayUs(5); // Stability delay
        sum+=Timer_Large_ReadCapture(); // Get low pulse duration in ms
    }
    sum/=10; // Get average

    uint16 senDat1=(int16)((sum)/2.0f); // Sensor transfer function

    sum=0;
    for(i=0;i<10;i++){ // Average of 10 measurements
        while(!PWM_Small_Read()); // Wait for previous pulse
        while(PWM_Small_Read()); // Wait for falling edge
        while(!PWM_Small_Read()); // Wait for rising edge
        CyDelayUs(5); // Stability delay
        sum+=Timer_Small_ReadCapture(); // Get low pulse duration in us
    }
    sum/=10; // Get average

    uint16 senDat2=(int16)((sum)/2.0f); // Sensor transfer function

    dat[0]=senDat1>>8;
    dat[1]=senDat1&0xFF;
    dat[2]=senDat2>>8;
    dat[3]=senDat2&0xFF;

    return dat;
}

/* [] END OF FILE */
```

6.1.3 MAIN.C routine for PWM (one pulse LED) sensors

```
/* =====
 * Air Quality Beacon, part of the hackAIR project.
 * Freely available under CC BY 4.0
 *
 *
 * Author: George Doxastakis gdoxastakis.ee@gmail.com
 * Technology Transfer & Smart Solutions
 * TEI of Athens
 * http://research.ee.teiath.gr/ttss/
 *
 * http://www.hackAIR.eu/
 */
#include <project.h>

/* Function prototypes */
void StackEventHandler(uint32 event, void* eventParam);
int16 readParticles();

/* ADV payload dta structure */
extern CYBLE_GAPP_DISC_MODE_INFO_T cyBle_discoveryModeInfo;
#define advPayload (cyBle_discoveryModeInfo.advData->advData)
```


D3.5: 1st Design Guidelines for Open Sensor fabrication

```
int main()
{
    CyGlobalIntEnable; /* Enable global interrupts. */

    /* Start CYBLE component and register the generic event handler */
    CyBle_Start(StackEventHandler);

    Timer_Start();
    for(;;)
    {
        int16 val=readParticles(); //Perform sensor measurement

        /* Dynamic payload will be continuously updated */
        advPayload[19] = 0x04; //Sensor ID: 0x04 for GP2Y1023AU0F
        advPayload[23] = val>>8; //High byte of sensor measurement
        advPayload[24] = val&0xFF; //Low byte of sensor measurement
        CyBle_GapUpdateAdvData(cyBle_discoveryModeInfo.advData,
        cyBle_discoveryModeInfo.scanRspData); //Update Advertisement Packet

        CyBle_ProcessEvents();

        CyDelay(500); //Measurement delay
    }
}

void StackEventHandler(uint32 event, void *eventParam)
{
    switch(event)
    {
        case CYBLE_EVT_STACK_ON:
            /* BLE stack is on. Start BLE advertisement */
            CyBle_GapStartAdvertisement(CYBLE_ADVERTISING_FAST);
            break;

        default:
            break;
    }
}

/*****
* NAME :          int16 readParticles()
*
* DESCRIPTION :   Read sensor measurement
* OUTPUTS :
*   int16 Dust concentration in ug/m^3
*/
int16 readParticles(){
    int i;
    int sum=0;

    for(i=0;i<10;i++){ // Average of 10 measurements
        while(!PWM_IN_Read()); // Wait for previous pulse
        while(PWM_IN_Read()); // Wait for falling edge
        while(!PWM_IN_Read()); // Wait for rising edge
        CyDelayUs(5); // Stability delay
        sum+=Timer_ReadCapture(); // Get low pulse duration in us
    }
    sum/=10; // Get average

    uint16 senDat=(int16)((sum-1400)/14.0f); // Sensor transfer function
}
```

```

    return senDat;
}

/* [] END OF FILE */

```

6.1.4 MAIN.C routine for serial output sensors

```

/* =====
 * Air Quality Beacon, part of the hackAIR project.
 * Freely available under CC BY 4.0
 *
 *
 * Author: George Doxastakis gdoxastakis.ee@gmail.com
 * Technology Transfer & Smart Solutions
 * TEI of Athens
 * http://research.ee.teiath.gr/ttss/
 *
 * http://www.hackAIR.eu/
 */
#include <project.h>

/* Function prototypes */
void StackEventHandler(uint32 event, void* eventParam);
char* readParticles();

/* ADV payload dta structure */
extern CYBLE_GAPP_DISC_MODE_INFO_T cyBle_discoveryModeInfo;
#define advPayload (cyBle_discoveryModeInfo.advData->advData)

int main()
{
    CyGlobalIntEnable; /* Enable global interrupts. */
    Serial_Start();
    /* Start CYBLE component and register the generic event handler */
    CyBle_Start(StackEventHandler);

    for(;;)
    {
        char *val=readParticles(); //Perform sensor measurement (waits for result)

        /* Dynamic payload will be continuously updated */
        advPayload[19] = 0x01; //Sensor ID: 0x01 for SEN0177
        advPayload[23] = val[4]; //High byte of PM1 value
        advPayload[24] = val[5]; //Low byte of PM1 value
        advPayload[25] = val[6]; //High byte of PM2.5 value
        advPayload[26] = val[7]; //Low byte of PM2.5 value
        advPayload[27] = val[8]; //High byte of PM10 value
        advPayload[28] = val[9]; //Low byte of PM10 value
        CyBle_GapUpdateAdvData(cyBle_discoveryModeInfo.advData,
cyBle_discoveryModeInfo.scanRspData); //Update Advertisement Packet
        CyBle_ProcessEvents();
    }
}

void StackEventHandler(uint32 event, void *eventParam)
{
    switch(event)
    {

        case CYBLE_EVT_STACK_ON:
            /* BLE stack is on. Start BLE advertisement */
            CyBle_GappStartAdvertisement(CYBLE_ADVERTISING_FAST);

```

D3.5: 1st Design Guidelines for Open Sensor fabrication

```
        break;

    default:
        break;
}

}

/*****
* NAME :          char* readParticles()
*
* DESCRIPTION :   Read sensor measurement
* OUTPUTS :      char* Sensor TX packet
*/
char* readParticles(){
    int idx;
    static char senData[32];
    senData[0]=0x42;
    while(Serial_UartGetChar() != 0x42); // Wait for start character
    for(idx=1;idx<32;idx++){ // Read TX packet
        CyDelay(10); // Wait for data
        senData[idx]=Serial_UartGetChar();// Get next byte
    }
    return senData;
}

/* [] END OF FILE */
```

All the corresponding files (project files as well as .hex files) will be available to users through the hackAIR platform.

6.2 Arduino sketches

The Arduino sketches that the user will need to shape will be simple and will be based on simple commands (see section 6.2.1) since the vast majority of sensor settings, calibration, configuration and connection parameters are embedded inside the library. Under this approach, the user has to provide the minimum effort to the already made Arduino sketches. There are two options for sketches: one for Ethernet connection and one for WiFi connection. Representative examples for one sensor are presented below (comments in green).

6.2.1 Arduino with Ethernet shield

```
/*
 * A generic example using the SHARP GP2Y1010AU0F sensor
 * and the Ethernet shield to communicate.
 */

#include "hackAIR.h"
#include "hackAIR-ethernet.h"

#define API_KEY          API-KEY-HERE

/* Ethernet Initialization */
byte mac[] = {
    0xAA, 0xBB, 0xCC, 0xDD, 0xEE, 0xFF
};

hackAIR sensor(SHARP_GP2Y1010AU0F);
int connected = 0;

void setup() {
    // Initialize the sensor
    sensor.begin();
```


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```
// Open serial port
Serial.begin(9600);

// Connect to the internet (DHCP)
Serial.write("Connecting with ethernet...");
if (Ethernet.begin(mac) == 0) {
  Serial.println("Unable to configure ethernet using DHCP");
} else {
  Serial.print("Connected using ");
  Serial.println(Ethernet.localIP());
  connected = 1;
}
delay(5000);
}

void loop() {
  // Take a reading
  float reading = sensor.readParticles();

  // Print it to serial
  Serial.print("Sensor value: ");
  Serial.print(reading);
  Serial.println(" mg/m^3");

  // Send it over the internet
  if (connected == 1) {
    Serial.println("Sending to server...");
    int success = hackAIRnet_send(API_KEY, reading);
    if (success == 0) {
      Serial.println("Sent successfully.");
    } else {
      Serial.println("Could not send! :(");
    }
  }
}

// Wait a bit
delay(1000);
}
```

6.2.2 Arduino with hackAIR WiFi shield

```
/*
 * A generic example using the SHARP GP2Y1010AU0F sensor
 * and the hackAIR WiFi shield to communicate.
 */

#include "hackAIR.h"
#include "hackAIR-wifi.h"
#define API_KEY          API-KEY-HERE
#define SSID              EXAMPLE-NETWORK
#define PASSWORD          NETWORK-PASSWORD

hackAIR sensor(SHARP_GP2Y1010AU0F);

void setup() {
  // Initialize the sensor
  sensor.begin();
  // Open the serial port for debugging
  Serial.begin(9600);
  // Initialize WiFi
  hackAIRWifi.init(API_KEY, SSID, PASSWORD);
}
```



```

}

void loop() {
  // Take a reading from the sensor
  float reading = sensor.readParticles();
  // Print it to serial
  Serial.print(reading);
  Serial.println(" ug/m^3");

  // Send through WiFi
  if (hackAIRWifi.connected == 1) {
    int success = hackAIRWifi.submit(reading);
    if (success == 0) {
      Serial.println("Successfully sent data with WiFi.");
    } else {
      Serial.println("Could not submit data through WiFi");
    }
  }
}
}

```

6.2.3 Arduino booting with ESP shield

```

#include <hackAIR-WiFi.h>
#include <hackAIR-Sense.h>

void setup() {
  // Initialize serial port & LED pin
  wifi.begin();
  pinMode(13, OUTPUT);
  /* Any and all sensors should also be setup here */
  // Ask the WiFi chipset to see if it has any
  // keys stored

  int keyStored = wifi.checkForKeys();
  if (keyStored == 0) {
    // No keys are stored, let's start in AP
    // mode.
    wifi.beginAP();
    // Now let's wait for the user to pick an AP
    while (wifi.waitForUser()) {
      delay(1000);
    }

    // Exit AP mode
    wifi.stopAP();
    // Connect to the internet
    int success = wifi.beginST();
    // If something went wrong, flash error LED
    if (success == 0) {
      while (1) {
        digitalWrite(13, HIGH);
        delay(500);
        digitalWrite(13, LOW);
        delay(500);
      }
    }
  }
}

void loop() {
  // The user should read from the sensor here
  float ppm10 = hackAIR.read10();
  float ppm5 = hackAIR.read5();
}

```

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```
// Send using the WiFi connection
wifi.submitData(ppm10, ppm5);
// The user should now take care of power management
// in case it's required. Both the sensor and the
// WiFi libraries will provide tools the user can
// use to minimize power consumption and thus increase
// battery life.
}
```

7 Implementation Guidelines

The following guidelines are provided in order to help the users implement the corresponding solution. For all the designs a set of common requirements regarding installation must be fulfilled as presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Installation and design specifications

Requirement	Implementation	Proposal
Unobstructed dust path	Open air path from inlet to outlet	Air inlet outlet through sunblinds or dense hole pattern Inlet must be obstacle free for at least 30cm
Protection from meteorological factors	Closed box with inlet/outlet in the vertical sides Box from non-transparent material in order to avoid strong light to reach the sensors (since the measurements are optical based)	Use of IP55 plastic cases or resin coated 3D-printed cases Avoid direct exposure to sun
Solid installation of electronics	Electronic boards and sensors must be secured tightly inside the box in order to meet the portability requirement	Use of commercial project boxes with perforated screw sockets 3D printed designs can prepare appropriate slots for snapping each module into place
Air tightness	Ideally all the air should enter the box inlet chamber and leave it from the outlet.	Users must ensure that the cover of the box seals completely. The use of sealing gaskets is highly recommended

7.1 BLEAir node

7.1.1 Suggested materials

The user will need the following components and materials to set up a BLEAir node:

- ✓ BLEAir Beacon PCB

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- Analog sensors PCB (use with DN7C3CA006, GP2Y1010AU0F, GP2Y1023AU0F, SM-PWM-01C and PPD42NS) – Figure 28
- Serial Sensor PCB (use with SEN0177) - Figure 28
- ✓ Dual male 1.2mm headers
- ✓ Male 1.2mm header (optional)
- ✓ 1x 150Ω Resistor
- ✓ 1x 220μF/16V electrolytic capacitor
- ✓ Dust density sensor (any sensor mentioned above)
- ✓ Sensor connector (provided by vendor)
- ✓ USB type-b female with shield (through hole connector)
- ✓ PSoC 4 BLE Module (CY8CKIT-142) or compatible
- ✓ MiniProg3 programmer and debugger or KitProg (included in CY8CKIT-059)
- ✓ A USB power bank (at least 3000mAh) for power supply

7.1.2 STEP 1: PCB Assembly

After constructing or receiving the BLEAir Beacon PCB, users proceed to the following steps:

- g) Solder the dual male headers to H1 and H2
- h) Solder the USB type-b component to U1
- i) Solder R1 and C1 (only on analog sensors PCB)
- j) If the sensor comes with a female header solder the male 1.2mm header in H3

7.1.3 STEP 2: Sensor Connection

For each type of sensor, users perform the following steps:

- For DN7C3CA006 connect:
 - Pin 1-6 to H3 Vcc - V_LED accordingly
 - Fan to V_FAN and GND
- For GP2Y1010AU0F connect:
 - PIN1 → V_LED
 - PIN2 → GND
 - PIN3 → LED
 - PIN4 → GND
 - PIN5 → Vout
 - PIN6 → Vcc
- For GP2Y1023AU0F connect:
 - PIN1 → Vout
 - PIN2 → GND
 - PIN3 → GND
 - PIN4 → V_LED
 - PIN5 → Vcc
- For SM-PWM-01C and PPD42NS connect:
 - PIN1 → GND
 - PIN2 → Vout
 - PIN3 → Vcc
 - PIN4 → LED
- For SEN0177 connect:
 - The sensor's TX pin to the board's RX_IN pin

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- Vcc and Gnd pins accordingly

7.1.4 STEP 3: Programming the PSoC 4 BLE Module using PSoC programmer

Before connecting the Bluetooth module to the board it has to be programmed with the proper algorithm using a USB Programmer and Cypress's PSoC Programmer software which can be downloaded from their website. To choose the proper code file for the sensor, users should follow these guidelines:

- Use AnalogLedSensor.hex for DN7C3CA006 and GP2Y1010AU0F
- Use SerialLaserSensor.hex for SEN0177
- Use PwmLedSensor.hex for GP2Y1023AU0F
- Use DualPulseLedSensor.hex for SM-PWM-01C and PPD42NS

After choosing the proper file, users proceed to the following steps to program the module:

- k) Connect Minipro3 (Figure 11) or KitProg (Figure 12) through the 6 pin header marked at the bottom left of the PSoC 4 module (check for matching pin names). KitProg example is shown in Figure 28

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Figure 28. Connecting KitProg to BLE module for programming

- l) Connect programmer to a USB 2.0 (or above) port (Figure 29)

Figure 29. KitProg connection to USB port

- m) Launch PSoC Programmer software
- n) Open the proper .hex file
- o) Select the device and click 'Program' (Figure 30)
- p) Connect the module to your PCB (using H1 and H2)

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Figure 30. Starting the programming process

7.1.5 STEP 3 (alternative): Programming the PSoC 4 BLE Module using PSoC Creator (for experienced users)

Before connecting the Bluetooth module to the board it has to be programmed with the proper algorithm using a USB Programmer and Cypress's PSoC Creator software which can be downloaded from their website.

- q) Install PSoC Creator
- r) Copy the *BLEair_Creator.rar* from hackAIR site
- s) Uncompress *BLEair_Creator.rar* in a folder inside MyDocuments (there must be one file called *AirQualityBeacons.cywrk* and 4 subfolders: *AnalogLedSensor.cydsn*, *DualPulseLedSensor.cydsn*, *PwmLedSensor.cydsn* and *SerialLaserSensor.cydsn*)
- t) Plug-in the BLE module to CY8CKIT-042 board (Figure 31)
- u) Open PSoC Creator
- v) Locate and load the file *AirQualityBeacons.cywrk*. This is the project file which loads all the files from all the four designs. Loaded files must be presented on the left pane.
- w) From all the loaded designs, only one is the active (which can be "burned" to PSoC 4 BLE) as shown in Figure 32
- x) Pressing the "Program" button the programming sequence starts (compiling, linking, debugging etc.) and finally "burns" the code to PSoC. A message of success will appear in the Output window Figure 33.

Figure 31. Plugging in the PSoC 4 BLE to CY8CKIT-042 development board

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Figure 32. PSoC creator with the project loaded (all the 4 designs are visible in the left pane). The active project marked bold

Figure 33. Initiation of programming sequence (by pressing the Program button indicated by red arrow) and successful programming of a PSoC module (messages inside green frame)

7.1.6 STEP 4: Test using an Android BLE enabled smartphone

After the device is ready users should check all connections and plug it in a USB port or Powerbank, then use a BLE enabled android device to check for incoming advertisement packets. The advertisement data can be easily viewed in hexadecimal format using iBeacon Detector, a free app available in the Google Play Store. Users can use the app to view their data (Figure 35) and identify them through the Air Quality Beacon data structure guide (Figure 18).

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To connect the Sharp GP2Y1010AU0F sensor to the WiFi Air Quality Shield users have to use the generic sensor I/O ports (P3 and P6) as presented in Figure 35 . Both screw terminals and pin header are connected internally so users can select what is more convenient for their project.

- Sensor pin 1 -> Shield VF pin (3)
- Sensor pin 2 -> Shield GND pin (5)
- Sensor pin 3 -> Shield IO1 pin (1)
- Sensor pin 4 -> Shield GND pin (5)
- Sensor pin 5 -> Shield IO2 pin (2)
- Sensor pin 6 -> Shield 5V pin (4)

With this setup, the shield uses the analog pins A0 and A1 from the Arduino board as well as digital pins 0, 1, 2 and 4 for communicating with the WiFi module. Everything else is available for use.

7.2.1.2 With breadboard/protoboard

The sensor connection should be done as follows:

- Sensor pin 1 -> Filter (see below)
- Sensor pin 2 -> GND
- Sensor pin 3 -> A0
- Sensor pin 4 -> GND
- Sensor pin 5 -> A1
- Sensor pin 6 -> 5V

This sensor requires a filter for one of the power lines. This filter can easily be constructed using one resistor (150Ω) and one capacitor (220μF) as shown in Figure 36.

Figure 36. Breadboard connection of sensor's power line filter

Detailed schematics are always available for the whole shield circuit. For using the WiFi module (ESP series) without the Air Quality shield users should always consult the detailed schematic due to the specific needs of the WiFi module (3.3V I/O and high current draw).

7.2.2 Software Setup

7.2.2.1 General/Serial

The sketch should begin by including the hackAIR library and creating a sensor:

```
#include <hackAIR.h>
```

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```
hackAIR sensor(SHARP_GP2Y1010AU0F);
```

In the setup() function users have to open the serial port and initialize the sensor.

```
void setup() {  
  // Open serial port  
  Serial.begin(9600);  
  
  // Initialize sensor  
  sensor.init();  
}
```

Whenever users want to take a reading they should use the readParticles() function of the library:

```
void loop() {  
  // Take a particle reading  
  float reading = sensor.readParticles();  
  
  // Send it through serial  
  Serial.begin(reading);  
}
```

For all the available functions of the library users should consult the official documentation.

7.2.2.2 Ethernet/WiFi

An API key is required to submit data to the hackAIR platform. Once users acquire their key, they should put it somewhere accessible in their code.

```
#include <hackAIR.h>  
#include <hackAIR-wifi.h> // Include if using WiFi  
#include <hackAIR-ethernet.h> // Include if using Ethernet  
  
#define API_KEY        YOUR-KEY-HERE  
#define SSID           YOUR-NETWORK           // For WiFi  
#define PASSWORD       YOUR-NETWORK-PASSWORD // For WiFi
```

In their setup() users must initialize either WiFi or Ethernet to connect to the internet.

```
// Ethernet  
byte mac[] = {  
  0xAA, 0xBB, 0xCC, 0xDD, 0xEE, 0xFF  
};  
if (Ethernet.begin(mac) == 0) {  
  Serial.println("Unable to configure ethernet using DHCP");  
} else {  
  Serial.print("Connected using ");  
  Serial.println(Ethernet.localIP());  
}  
  
// WiFi  
if (hackAIRWifi.init(API_KEY, SSID, PASSWORD) == 0) {  
  Serial.println("Unable to connect to WiFi network.");  
} else {  
  Serial.println("Connected.");  
}
```

Now that the network connection is established, users should take a reading as described in the *Generic/Serial* section and send it over to the platform.

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```
// Take a reading from the sensor
float reading = sensor.readParticles();
// Ethernet
int success = hackAIRnet_send(API_KEY, reading);
if (success == 0) {
  Serial.println("Successfully sent data with WiFi.");
} else {
  Serial.println("Could not submit data through WiFi");
}
// WiFi
int success = hackAIRWifi.submit(reading);
if (success == 0) {
  Serial.println("Successfully sent data with WiFi.");
} else {
  Serial.println("Could not submit data through WiFi");
}
```

7.3 COTS

7.3.1 Materials

- Air pump of known capacity
- Coffee filter
- Rubber
- Clip lens
- Smartphone

7.3.2 Implementation instructions

- y) Cut a piece filter (size of a 2 euros coin)
- z) Attach the filter tightly to the inflation part of the filter
- aa) Use a rubber band so that the filter won't move
- bb) Turn on the Air pump
- cc) Leave it turned for a specific time
- dd) Turn of the Air pump
- ee) Remove the rubber band
- ff) Remove carefully the filter
- gg) Take a picture with your smartphone using clip lens
- hh) Upload the picture

8 Works Cited

- [1] E. Austin, I. Novosselov, E. Seto and M. Yost, "Laboratory Evaluation of the Shinyei PPD42NS Low-Cost Particulate Matter Sensor," *PloS one*, no. dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0137789, 2015.
- [2] J. C. K. M. M. Arling, "Air quality sensor network for Philadelphia," 2010.
- [3] Sharp, "<http://www.sharp-world.com/products/device/lineup/selection/opto/dust/index.html>," [Online].
- [4] Plantower, "<http://www.plantower.com/content/?94.html>," [Online].
- [5] A. Morpugro, F. Pedersini and A. Reina, "A low-cost instrument for environmental particulate analysis based on optical scattering," in *IEEE Instrumentation and Measurement Technology Conference (I2MTC)*, 2012.
- [6] "<http://www.dylosproducts.com/dcproairqumo.html>," Dylos. [Online].
- [7] i. Sharp, "http://www.sharpsma.com/webfm_send/1488," [Online].
- [8] i. Sharp, "http://media.digikey.com/pdf/Data%20Sheets/Sharp%20PDFs/DN7C3CA006_Spec.pdf," [Online].
- [9] Amphenol, "<http://gr.mouser.com/pdfdocs/01Cdustsensor datasheet-English1-22-3.pdf>," [Online].
- [10] i. Sharp, "<http://media.digikey.com/pdf/Data%20Sheets/Sharp%20PDFs/GP2Y1023AU0F%20Specs.pdf>," [Online].
- [11] Shinyei, "http://wiki.seeedstudio.com/wiki/Grove_-_Dust_sensor," [Online].
- [12] i. Plantower, "https://www.google.gr/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=2&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0ahUKEwiK7rSc85XPAhWhCsAKHeuPBB0QFggHMAE&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.plantower.com%2Fen%2Fcontent%2F%3F108.html&usg=AFQjCNFvycVx7qJ7CMsnFUHZtrA0Rh3pw&sig2=ZnHJl-dXa_OecgCMt--KnQ," [Online].
- [13] NovaFitness, "https://www.google.gr/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=4&ved=0ahUKEwjPq_P78pXPAhXHDMAKHUL3BasQFgg4MAM&url=http%3A%2F%2Fbreathe.indiaspend.org%2Fwp-content%2Fuploads%2F2015%2F11%2Fnova_laser_sensor.pdf&usg=AFQjCNFp3mrXRfBTTe2iyLFZldxzqXgmhw&sig2=pKNO," [Online].
- [14] J. Lindh, "Bluetooth Low Energy beacons," Texas Instruments, 2015.
- [15] Arduino/Genuino, "www.arduino.cc," [Online].
- [16] Cypress, "<http://www.cypress.com/file/290246>," [Online].
- [17] "<https://www.fasttech.com/product/2282705-lieqi-lq-006-clip-on-6x-macro-scope-lens-for>," [Online].
- [18] i. Sharp, "http://media.digikey.com/pdf/Data%20Sheets/Sharp%20PDFs/DN7C3CA006_Spec.pdf," [Online].